

PRISMA 2020 Checklist

Mapping Research Trends on Digital Transformation in Government: A Bibliometric Analysis and Research Agenda"

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist Item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	Page 1
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist.	Page 1
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	Page 2-4
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	Page 4
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for synthesis.	Page 6-7, Table 2
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify date when each source was last searched.	Page 7
Search strategy	7	Present full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used.	Page 7, Table 1
Selection process	8	Specify methods used to decide study inclusion, including how many reviewers screened each record and report, and if independently.	Page 7-8, figure 1
Data collection process	9	Specify methods used to collect data, including reviewer numbers and independence.	Page 8
Data items	10a	List and define outcomes for which data were sought.	Page 9-12
	10b	List and define other variables for data extraction; describe assumptions about missing or unclear information.	Not reported
Study risk of bias assessment	11	Specify methods used to assess risk of bias, tools used, and independence of reviewers.	Not reported

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist Item	Location where item is reported
Effect measures	12	Specify effect measures used in synthesis or presentation of results.	Not applicable (narrative synthesis)
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe processes to decide eligible studies for each synthesis.	Not reported
	13b	Methods required to prepare data for synthesis, handling missing statistics.	Not reported
	13c	Methods used to tabulate or visually display results.	Page 9-17, Figures 2-12
	13d	Methods used to synthesize results; rationale provided.	Not reported
	13e	Methods used to explore causes of heterogeneity among results (e.g. subgroup analysis).	Not reported
	13f	Sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of results.	Not reported
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results.	Not reported
Certainty assessment	15	Describe methods used to assess certainty (confidence) in body of evidence.	Not reported
RESULTS			
Study selection	16a	Describe search results and selection process, use flow diagram.	Page 8-9
	16b	Cite excluded studies and reasons for exclusion.	Not reported
Study characteristics	17	Cite included studies and present characteristics.	Page 9-12, Figures 3-6
Risk of bias in studies	18	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	Not reported
Results of individual studies	19	Present summary statistics and effect estimates for each study (structured tables or plots).	Not reported
Results of syntheses	20a	Summarise characteristics and risk of bias among studies contributing to each synthesis.	Page 12-17
	20b	Results of statistical syntheses conducted (if meta-analysis).	Not applicable (narrative synthesis)
	20c	Investigations of causes of heterogeneity.	Page 12-17
	20d	Results of sensitivity analyses.	Not reported
Reporting biases	21	Assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (reporting biases).	Not reported
Certainty of evidence	22	Assessments of certainty (confidence) in body of evidence.	Not reported

DISCUSSION

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist Item	Location where item is reported
Discussion	23a	General interpretation of results in context of other evidence.	Page 18-23
	23b	Discuss limitations of included evidence.	Page 18-23
	23c	Discuss limitations of review processes used.	Page 18-23
	23d	Implications of results for practice, policy, future research.	Page 18-23
OTHER INFORMATION			
Registration and protocol	24a	Provide registration information or state if not registered.	Not reported
	24b	Indicate where review protocol can be accessed, or state if not prepared.	Not reported
	24c	Amendments to information provided at registration/protocol.	Not reported
Support	25	Sources of financial or non-financial support for review; funders' roles.	Not reported
Competing interests	26	Declare competing interests of review authors.	Not reported
Availability of data, code, materials	27	Indicate public availability and location of data, code, materials.	Not reported